

Visual Impairment Students Inclusion using Digital Fabrication Technologies: Collaborative Development of Chemistry Learning Support Tools

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Abstract

This case study aims to share a collaborative workflow to develop a chemistry science ludic learning tool, accessible to both, normal vision (NV), and blind, and low vision impaired (BLV) students. A 3D model was designed, seeking to facilitate chemical elements' electrons configuration representation, using information from the periodic table. The model was transformed into a physical product using digital fabrication technologies, allowing to reproduce Braille captions into each product component. Three-step developmental procedures, guided by a user-centered design process, include: (A) physical representation design, (B) appropriate digital manufacturing technology selection and fabrication, (C) user testing. Within these processes, 3D printing versatile application, and its capabilities to be complemented with CNC milling and laser cutting technologies was tested. Preliminary results, collected following UX testing processes, show the potential of digital fabrication technologies as democratic technological tools that could support customized products manufacturing, to foster most vulnerable communities such as BLV's students. Thus, its future applications could help to overcome local problems, and barriers.

Keywords

digital fabrication technologies, collaborative human-center design, blind and low vision impaired, visual impairment education, user experience

1 Introduction

Vision is considered the most dominant of our senses due to its crucial role throughout our day-to-day activities (WHO, 2019). Nonetheless, the population suffering visual impairment (VI) keeps increasing (Ackland et al., 2017), affecting 29% of the global population (WHO, 2019). Annually, its expected impact in the global economy would surpass US\$3 trillion, in productivity lost and health and social care require investments. Whilst, 237 million suffer moderate to severe visual impairment (MSVI), 39 million people remain blindness, with major prevalence in low-income countries (Laser Eye Surgery Hub, 2020). Furthermore, by 2050, blind and visually impaired (BVI) population are expected to reach 703 million

people (Ackland et al., 2017). This context, draws the importance to foster, and support social and economic inclusion of those blind and low visually impaired (BLV). And undoubtedly, education sector has a key role (WHO, 2019). However, education accessibility, especially in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) remains limited due to different factors (Asebriy et al., 2018; Beck-Winchatz & Riccobono, 2008; Rule et al., 2011). As per its heavily graphic representations demands some limitations regarding BLV students' special needs are found (Arcand et al., 2019; Fraser & Maguvhe, 2008), and raise questions regarding their educational process complexity and challenges.

In recent decades, an effort has been made to create strategies and generate technologies that integrate the BLV population (Asebriy et al., 2018; Campbell, 2019; Stefik et al., 2011). Multisensory strategies, which integrate to the education process the senses (touch, vision, hearing, etc.), have proven to be successful for BLV students' STEM teaching, improve the cognitive process by increasing interest, curiosity, motivation and attitude towards a unit of content (Campbell, 2019). And for this matter, ICTs implementation, as tools to support these kinds of strategies, are gaining advocates.

NASA and National Center for Blind Youth in Science (NCBYS) get involved in developing resources for astronomy learning along different levels of instruction (Arcand et al., 2020). Moreover, Moodle, a well-known web-based educational platform, launched in 2019 a version for BLV students, and reported a 45% improvement on their educational performance. Technology-based devices have also been used to foster STEM related skills (Batanero Concha et al., 2019). ShapeCad presents a proposal for BLV people to interact and modify CAD files by tactile methods (Siu et al., 2019). While, CamIO integrates AI using a camera and describing, by audio, framed objects (Shen et al., 2013). Nevertheless, does the inclusion of BLV students on STEM learning rely on hearing-dependable devices? Is there any possibility to develop low-cost customized tools looking for integrating developing countries' BLV students?

These research questions were the starting point to carry out a human-centric collaborative design process for developing a new chemistry element ordering model allowing a physical representation as a tool to underpin a multisensory experience at low-cost. The literature review suggests that there is a starting research trend focused on chemistry for BLV education. Therefore, BLV community involvement in the design process is crucial to assure educational tools fit and usability. The novel ordering model attempts to simplify the traditional periodic table representation model and improve the BLV students' learning process. By sorting the elements into concentric circumferences that represent electronic charge orbits (s,p,d,f,...), proposes to group each element according to its last electron location. Thus, the model facilitates the atomic symbol and atomic number recognition, and allows an easiest way to explain basic concepts, such as atomic structures and electronic configuration.

The conceptual new ordering model brought the opportunity to develop physical learning resources to test its feasibility as tools to enhance BLV students' chemistry learning process. Developmental procedure, followed a human centric design process, and applied iterative and incremental prototyping and testing, as key points to assure project success. This article aims to describe a collaborative three-steps developmental process for learning resources, oriented to include the BLV community: (a) physical representation design, (b) appropriate digital manufacturing technology selection and fabrication, (c) user testing. In addition, it aims to expose digital manufacturing technologies potential as democratic technological tools. Thus, to rapidly include braille writing, a 3D printing manufacturing process was applied, and complemented by subtractive CNC milling and laser cutting technologies application.

This study attempted to share the collaborative workflow applied to develop an innovative learning tool tailored for the BLV community, and that could be extended to develop products and services oriented to users with similar disparities. Furthermore, it contributes to exposing the potential of digital fabrication technologies as democratic technology tools that underpins its application to solve local problems, surpass barriers, and attend to the most vulnerable groups.

2 Methodology and applications

2.1 Physical representation design

Learning objective

Our aim was to propose a physical tool that could foster a better understanding of the chemical elements arrangement that could be also accessible for BLV students. The idea was focused on developing a new 3D model to order chemical elements, as a didactic strategy for learning, based on a ludic tool. Our baseline was the common 2D periodic table, where chemical elements are represented in order based on their atomic numbers. Thus, considering that even for normal vision students it is difficult to understand concepts such as electronic configuration, valence level, atomic number, and family groups, we considered that the physical prototype must also include them. Furthermore, the idea was to address the difficulties regarding atomic representation and location of each chemical elements' electrons. This approach is expected to improve comprehension of these topics that usually require graphic representations, something very complex for BLV students. Hence, we considered that through physical interactions with a board and spheres could help us to develop a 3D model, incorporating Braille dots. Then, teachers could introduce a tool that could promote all kinds of students' interest, pursuing to become an inclusive and complementary tool for chemistry teaching.

Model description

First step was to develop a 3D modelling, transforming the typical 2D chemical elements periodic table. Its graphic 3D representation aims to link prior chemical concepts. We take as a point of reference, elements' atomic electron distribution representation, usually seen as an abstract concept, transforming it into a visual and physical model. The following concepts were applied to develop a physical modeling

- *Electronic configuration*: Represents atoms' electrons distribution, and determines most of the chemical behavior of an element. It brings basic information to place a chemical element on the periodic table, and subshells. It represents the standard notation used to describe the electronic structure of an atom.
- *Orbital angular momentum quantum number (ℓ)*: Called subshell, represented by "s, p, d, f" letters, are used to distribute the number of electrons. For our 3D modelling, we decide to represent each subshell with a circumference, thus, we draw four (4) concentric circles representing them.
- *Chemical elements*: Currently, 118 chemical elements are known, each of them present a unique electronic configuration, which could help us to find out the outermost element's shell and subshell, and the number of electrons within them. Each chemical element is graphically represented by a sphere, each of them placed in a specific order around the concentric circumferences (s, p, d, and f subshells).
- *Chemical elements' atomic number*: Indicates each element's number of protons in its nucleus. Further, determines how many electrons surround its nucleus, and allows to place them in order into the periodic table. Within the 3D proposed model, the atomic number will be described on each spheres' surface.
- *Energy level*: Provides information about orbitals (subshells) energy levels. Undertaking an analysis regarding each of the 118 chemical elements' energy levels, we found out that elements at the (a) subshell "s" reach seven different energy levels, (b) subshell "p" up to six, (c) subshell "d" up to four, and (d) subshell "f" each two energy level. In our case, this information serves to divide each concentric circumference in "sections".
- *Principal quantum number at the last atom subshell*: Appoints atom's energy level at the last subshell of its electronic configuration. Each subshell holds a maximum number of electrons, (a) subshell "s" - 2, (b) subshell "p" - 6 (c) subshell "d" - 10, and (d) subshell "f" - 14. Within the 3D model, this maximum number of electrons allows us to establish "positions" within each "section".

- *Chemical elements family*: Into the periodic table, elements with the most similar properties are placed in the same group, represented by a vertical column indicating that they share similar physical and chemical characteristics. In the 3D model families are recognized by elements localized at equal “positions” in every subshell “section”.

s subshell	p subshell	d subshell	f subshell
$\ell = 0$	$\ell = 1$	$\ell = 2$	$\ell = 3$
$m_\ell = 0$	$m_\ell = -1, 0, +1$	$m_\ell = -2, -1, 0, +1, +2$	$m_\ell = -3, -2, -1, 0, +1, +2, +3$
One s orbital	Three p orbitals	Five d orbitals	Seven f orbitals
7 energy levels	6 energy levels	4 energy levels	2 energy levels
2 s orbital electrons	6 p orbital electrons	10 d orbital electrons	14 f orbital electrons

Table 1. Breakdown and Properties of subshells.
Adapted from Relation Between Quantum Numbers and Atomic Orbitals, by Chang, 2010, p.297.

The proposed 3D model will pretend to highlight specific concepts that students could link to specific physical actions, such as location and distribution within graphic concentric circumferences. Thus, each subshell will be represented by concentric circumferences, according to the type of orbital (s,p,d and f) as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: 2D and 3D view of the ordering according to the type of Subshell (Source: authors' elaboration)

Within each subshell, the 118 chemical elements, each one represented by little spheres, simulating electrons, will be distributed and located regarding their atomic numbers, in ascending order, up to their energy level at their last subshell (See figure 2).

Figure 2. Model of ordering of chemical elements by Subshell
 Source: Authors' elaboration

Each chemical element electron configuration is unique, and serves as a point of reference to obtain the energy level reached, and the number of electrons at its last subshell. We present the Calcium (Ca) atom's electrons configuration as a reference (See Figure 3).

Figure 3. Electrons configuration of Calcium (Ca)
 Source: Authors' elaboration

2.2 Digital manufacturing technology selection and fabrication process

The physical model was drawn as embodied on a board with milling channels representing each subshell, where each element sphere could be placed. Furthermore, we could add any new circumference needed to locate any new chemical elements, starting from atomic number 121, whose configuration will need subshell "g". The current 2D chemical elements distribution into the periodic table does not allow to place any new element.

Whilst, this model could provide a connection with previous concepts in order to facilitate learning practices for normal vision students, could also promote BLV community inclusion. By placing information in the Braille writing system in each sphere, regarding elements' symbol, atomic number, students could identify each element subshell (s, p, d, f), and determine its section and position. Thus, each sphere could be physically placed on a baseboard. For BLV's students guidelines, 3D printing labels could be also embroidered, specifying subshells type, section, and position. Additionally, a generic sphere could be printed, as a physical reference for the captions distributed within each sphere, as shown in Table 2.

item symbol	item description	Braille name of item	item detail
Q	Element symbol	symbol	
119	Atomic Number	Z	
q	Subshell	layer	
7	Principal Quantum Number	section	
13	Number of electrons	position	

Table 2. Generic Element Sphere Information Details.

Procedures considerations

This section shows the prototype's fabrication process applied, describing from its 3D digital modeling to its physical manufacture.

Prototype's digital modeling

1. Due to its physical requirements, the prototype was designed with 4 components: (a) a baseboard; (b) spheres, representing the chemical elements; (c) concentric circumference labels, to include Braille descriptions, and (d) a shield.
2. Prototype design was planned using 3 different materials, and applying 3 digital manufacturing technologies (laser cutting, CNC milling and 3D printing). Thus, material and technology selection defined specific 3D designs considerations.
3. The 3D model was developed using Autodesk Inventor Professional software, based on surface modeling, applying basic commands such as extrude, emboss, revolve, and fillet (See figure 4).

Figure 4. Prototype modeling

4. Baseboard design dimensions (600mm x 600mm x 38mm), were established regarding the number and volume of elements' physical spheres, and their distribution in each concentric circumference. Thus, the 118 spheres could be placed throughout each one. CNC Milling technology was considered to be the most appropriate technology for its manufacture (See figure 5).

Figure 5. Baseboard 3D Model

5. A Shield (580 mm x 580 mm x 3 mm) was designed to protect the baseboard, and serve as a physical point of reference to BLV students, facilitating circumferences' identification. We applied laser cutting technology to place 4 circumferences (See figure 6).

Figure 6. Shield 3D Model

6. Physical spheres representing each 118 chemical elements were digitally modelled to include a unique Braille description. Sphere dimension (29 mm) was established considering ergonomic features, and information distribution. Hence, 3D Printing technology was considered as the most appropriate to reproduce Braille dots. Thus, 3D designs were developed according to Barczyk (2016), with a 1.6 mm base diameter, and 0.9 mm nominal height. Furthermore, the following features were included in their design:
7. A circumference placed as “Z-axis” point of reference at the top, for BLV’s students, as a guideline to identify Braille’s reading starting point (See figure 7).

Figure 7. Circumference top reference.

- a. An “L” shape was located at the front, connected to the circle top reference, allowing to identify Braille’s reading direction to follow (See figure 8).

Figure 8. “L” shape reference.

- b. Each sphere body contains elements’ symbols embossed on the surface, Accompanied by extruded Braille dots for BLV’s students (See figure 9).

Figure 9. Element symbol and braille writing.

- c. Following a clockwise rotation, we embossed elements' atomic number (Z), elements’ last subshell, energy level, and number of electrons at the last subshell (See figure 10).

Figure 10. Chemical Elements 3D Description

8. four (04) Concentric circumferences' labels were designed to be placed at the baseboard, in order to guide BLV's students. Information placed aims to bring orientation regarding each element's section and position into a subshell "s, p, d, f" sub-shells. 3D Printing was considered as the appropriate manufacturing technology (See figure 11).

Figure 11. Braille dots subshells "s, p, d, f" labels.

Each labels contain the following features:

- 1st Circumference, "s" orbital, with 235 mm outside diameter, presents 7 sections. Each section is divided in 2 (positions), the maximum number of electrons in each section.
- 2nd Circumference, "p" orbital, with 325 mm outside diameter, shows 6 sections. Each section is divided in 6 (positions), the maximum number of electrons in each section.
- 3rd Circumference, "d" orbital, with 415 mm outside diameter, showing 4 sections. Each section is divided in 10 (positions), the maximum number of electrons in each section.
- 4th Circumference, "f" orbital, with 505 mm outside diameter, showing 2 sections. Each section is divided in 14 (positions), the maximum number of electrons in each section.

Prototype fabrication

1. **Baseboard:** CNC milling was considered the most efficient technology for a subtractive process due to its dimensions, and requirements, as follow:
 - a. **Material selection:** Due to the baseboard's height requirement (38 mm), and without commercially available material to reach this thickness, we use three MDF sheets of 15 mm forming a “sandwich structure”. Medium Density Fibreboard (MDF) was chosen because of its great response against buckling failure (Wong, et. al, 2021), unlike plywood or OSB boards.
 - b. **CNC milling layout setup:** We used a Shopbot 3-axis milling machine (PRSalph model), PartWorks3D software for machining process configuration, and Vcarve Pro software to obtain a .gcode file for the manufacturing process (See Table 3). Total milling process took 570 minutes (See Figure 12)

Process	Tool	Diameter	RPM
Rough	End mill	0.5 inch	12000
Finish	Ball nose	0.25 inch	12000
Cut out	End mill	0.5 inch	12000

Table 3. Milling process parameters.

Figure 12. Finish process (25%) - Shopbot PRS Alpha.

2. **Shield:** Fabricated using laser cutting technology, due to design thickness requirements (<10 mm).
 - a. **Material selection:** 3mm transparent plexi-sheet (methyl methacrylate).
 - b. **Laser cutting layout settings:** A Trotec Speedy 400 was used. Cutting lines were configured using Corel Draw software (red color line, and < 0.1 mm thickness), and engraving areas (defined by black color line or hatch, and thickness). Corel Draw software needs to be synchronized with Trotec's machining software (Job Control), thus, we can configure speed, power, and frequency parameters (See figure 13 and 14). Total cutting process took 20 minutes.

Figure 13. Laser cutting at 75% - Trotec Speedy 400.

Figure 14. Shield final prototype.

3. **Spheres and concentric circumferences' labels:** 3D printing technology was chosen to manufacture each element representation due to the possibility to print Braille dots. Spheres were fabricated with FDM 3D printing technologies using PLA, and ABS materials, and by stereolithography process (SLA 3D printer) using grey resin. Braille dots need a high tactile definition, thus, 3D printing technology selection is crucial to test user experience (UX), due to their differences regarding product resolution, and surface quality.

- a. **Spheres prototyping for testing:** We selected 6 of the 118 elements for UX testing, due to their element symbols, atomic number, section and position reading complexity. Selected elements were: Oganesson (Og), Erbium (Er), Thulium (Tm), Mercury (Hg), Oxygen (O), and Magnesium (Mg). Each of them were fabricated with three different 3D printers, with specific characteristics, and parameters (See tables 4 & 5 and figure 15).

Figure 15. Prints comparison.

Item	Type	3D Printer	Resolution	Material
Printing 1	FDM	Flashprint Guider II	120 microns	PLA
Printing 2	FDM	Zortrax M200	190 microns	ABS
Printing 3	FDM	Zortrax M200	90 microns	ABS
Printing 4 y 5	SLA	Formlabs Form 3	100 microns	Grey Resin

Table 4. Printing records according to type of printing, resolution and material.

Item	Material quantity	Printing time	Post-processing time	Approximate local cost
Printing 1	56 g	499 min	-	26.15 USD
Printing 2	45 g	368 min	-	19.55 USD
Printing 3	44 g	673 min	-	32.97 USD
Printing 4	92 ml	338 min	60 min	84.40 USD
Printing 5	50 ml	339 min	60 min	58.00 USD

Table 5. Printing records according to material quantity, time and cost

Due to spheres' geometry, a great number of supports are needed when 3D printing (See Figures 16, 17 and 18). Post-process requires their removal, generating some tactile imperfections on each sphere's final surface. For SLA technology, we considered two (2) different 3D printing designs. Desing-1 was fully printed, while the second one (Desing-2) was vacuum printed, with 3mm spherical surface thickness, with two holes at "Z" axis bottom for printing requirements.

Figure 16. PLA-FDM printing using Guider II (Flashforge™)

Figure 17. ABS-FDM printing. Using M200 (Zortrax™)

Figure 18. SLA 3D printing using Form 3 (Formlabs™).

For SLA 3D printing, two additional post-processes are required, washing and curing. We used FormWash and FormCure machines for each process (See Figures Nº 19 y 20).

Figure 19. FormWash Process.

Figure 20. FormCure Process

b. 118 Spheres Manufacturing Process:

We can summaries different prototypes fabrication requirements in the following table:

Technology	Material	Resolution (microns)	Number of Batches	Printing time (hours)	Printing Timeframe (days)	Washing process Timeframe (days)	Curing process Timeframe (days)	Material Required	Estimated General Cost (USD)
FDM	PLA	120	10	167	9	-	-	1.12 kg	527.00
FDM	ABS	190	10	123	7	-	-	0.94 kg	395.00
FDM	ABS	90	10	225	12	-	-	0.94 kg	665.00
SLA (Design -1)	Resin	100	10	110	6	0.5	0.5	1.85 L	1689.00
SLA (Design -2)	Resin	100	10	110	6	0.5	0.5	1 L	1213.00

Table 6. 3D printing record of all 118 elements.

- c. **Concentric circumferences' labels:** Printer selection considered its geometric shape. Thus, FDM technology provides a high quality resolution when printing flat shapes. Labels were finally printed using a Guider II printer (Flashforge™) due to its major print bed's area (See figure 21).

Figure 21. Printing Guider II.

- d. **Final prototypes:** Each different printing technology only modified the prototype's physical appearance (See figure 22).

Figure 22. 3D Model final prototype.

2.3 C) User Testing

Testing process was developed in two stages, first one to collect information regarding methodologies, and tools applied by normal vision (NV) chemical teachers, and last stage to look for the 3D modelling validation, divided into two user segments; NV, and BLV's teachers.

– 1st stage: Exploratory Process

Our aim was to discover current chemistry teaching methodologies and tools, focused on electron configurations of chemical elements topic, and the traditional periodic table use. Thus, we could register teachers' commonly expected outcomes. Main results showed that all different methodologies and tools (graphics, software, or exercises) were applied to explain each chemical element's characteristics based on information placed on the traditional periodic table. Furthermore, in order to explain electron configuration, electron distribution within subshells, all teachers used Moeller's diagram.

– 2nd stage: Model Validation

1st iteration - proof of concept using card-based design: Applied to validate relationship between concepts and 3D model's components, and the flow chart of the potential teaching process to follow. We collected information from 11 NV's chemistry teachers (See table Nº 7). We ask for our proposed model's usefulness as a ludic learning tool with potential learning benefits. In this context, we sought first to pursue teachers' feedback regarding the flow chart, by placing informative cards into, what they considered as the most convenient flux. Then we conducted interviews, to collect qualitative data regarding their perception towards difficulty, logic, and content delivered.

Teaching level	Gender	Age range	Number of teachers	3D Model Usefulness Validation	
				Yes	No
High School	W	40-50	1	1	
	M		1	1	
University	W	30-45	0		
	M		4	4	
University	W	46-60	3	3	
	M		3	1	2

Table 7. Proof of concept's results.

2nd iteration - sphere's physical characteristic validation: At this stage we focused on BLV's teachers and general population. We obtained feedback from a blind teacher, and two BLV's past students. We asked whether information placed with Braille dots, on spheres printed with PLA material, can be read without any inconvenience, or whether we need to improve printing quality texture, change printing material, increase sphere volume, and other special features .

At each interview, we explained its purpose, and basic concepts related to the periodic table, and its chemical elements. Finally, we collect essential information regarding tactile features on spheres' surface allowing them to establish reading orientation, Braille dots physical perception, and information distribution. For this matter, four different prototypes (See table 8) were presented to each potential user. Further, it was necessary to provide physical orientation to each interviewee to localize reading starting point, and correct orientation for each prototype.

Additionally, each sample considered different design properties applied to Braille dots (tactile texture, diameter, and height).

number	test characteristics	Braille Dots design properties	prototype material	3D printer	Prototype photo
#1	3D Printing only includes chemical element's symbol, and its caption on Braille dots. The prototype was designed using Inventor software.	Regular extruded (Diameter = 1.5 mm. & Height = 0.9 mm.)	PLA	FlashForge Creator Pro	
#2	The elements subshell and the atomic number and their caption on Braille dots were added following clockwise orientation (Symbol, subshell, and atomic number were placed on the sphere surface).	Regular extruded (Diameter = 1.5 mm. & Height = 0.45 mm.)	PLA	FlashForge Guider II	
#3	A modified Prototype #2 design was developed using Rhinoceros software in order to improve Braille dots design.	Regular extruded (Diameter = 1.5 mm. & Height = 0.9 mm.) Top border was filleted to to decrease 3D printing roughness.	PLA	FlashForge Creator Pro	
#4	A modified Prototype #3 was printed changing information order (Symbol, atomic number, and subshell), looking to test better clockwise reading effectiveness.	Regular extruded (Diameter = 1.5 mm. & Height = 0.9 mm.) Top border was filleted to to decrease 3D printing roughness.	PLA	FlashForge Creator Pro	

Table 8. 2nd iteration's prototypes content characteristics

Main qualitative data collected for each prototype are presented at the following table (See table 9):

test	test result
#1	Wrinkled texture due to printing layers (layer height), rough to the touch.
	The user was able to read the text, understanding the information placed without any problems.
#2	Softer texture, but with difficulties to read Braille dots due to its height.

test	test result
	A writing error was detected at the atomic number's Braille caption.
	Reading and message capture was affected, reading timeframe was longer than expected
#3	At this stage users seem to be more comfortable and appealing when reading, due to previous prototypes testing, improving starting reading point location.
	Braille dots texture was qualified as suitable, being slightly rough to the touch.
	Better feedback regarding filleted points was captured.
	The user was able to read the text, however, information location, and order was questioned.
#4	Braille dots were easily readed and the user was able to understand the information placed without any inconveniences.
	Braille dots texture was qualified as suitable, being slightly rough to the touch. Users were able to recognize a better information distribution.
	Everyone concludes that this one was the best sample.

Table 9. 2nd iteration main results

Taking into account 2nd users test feedback, prototypes were improve by:

- Placing a "Z-axis" point of reference (a extruded small circumference was included at the top)
- Including an "L" shape figure, connected upwards to the top referencing point. Acting as a vertical belt, it will guide clockwise reading starting point.

- *3rd iteration - sphere's physical features validation:*

At this stage, feedback regarding referencing points' effectiveness were collected. Further, information placed into each sphere surface was: element symbol, atomic number, subshell, and section, and position numbers. Five testings were carried out following specifications described in table 10:

number	3D printing parameters	Braille Dots design properties	Printed Volume	prototype material	Printer 3D	Prototype Photo
#1	Resolution = 120 microns (high PLA quality)	Diameter = 1.5 mm. Height = 0.9 mm.	Full	PLA	Guider II	
#2	Resolution = 190 microns (standard ABS quality)	Diameter = 1.6 mm. Height = 1 mm.	Full	ABS	Zortrax	

number	3D printing parameters	Braille Dots design properties	Printed Volume	prototype material	Printer 3D	Prototype Photo
#3	Resolution = 90 microns (high ABS quality).	Diameter = 1.6 mm. Height = 1 mm	Full	ABS	Zortrax	
#4	Resolution = 100 microns (standard SLA quality).	Diameter = 1.6 mm. Height = 1 mm	Full	SLA RESIN	Form 3	
#5	Resolution = 100 microns (standard SLA quality).	Diameter = 1.6 mm. Height = 1 mm	Vacuum (spherical surface thickness = 3mm)	SLA RESIN	Form 3	

Table 10. 3rd iteration's prototypes content features

Main qualitative feedback regarding each prototype are detailed as follow (See table 11):

test	test result
#1	Rough to the touch.
	Users were able to read Braille captions with some difficulties due to wrinkled layers.
	Both points of reference were found useful
#2	Less rough to the touch in comparison with Prototype # 1
	Users were able to read Braille captions with less difficulties in comparison with prototype #1, stating smoothed wrinkles due to printing layers. Information placed was easily understood.
	Both points of reference were found useful
#3	Improved Braille dots tactile features were stated.
	Users still found more smoothed wrinkles due to printing layers.
	Both points of reference were found useful
#4	Users appointed a major improvement on Braille dots tactile features. Texture was considered smoother.
	Easily to read due to wrinkles absent, thus caption were more easily to identify
	Both points of reference were found useful

test	test result
	Residual printing support provoked users reading disorientation
#5	Sphere weight differences were not found important
	Printing holes were not considered as barriers to localize referencing print or to get confused with Braille captions reading.
	The lower roughness continues to be felt due to the supports.
	Residual printing support provoked users reading disorientation

Table 11. 3rd iteration main results

3 Conclusions

Collected results showed that a 3D modelling design developed to explain electrons configuration, provee to be potentially useful. 82% of teachers' feedback was positive, stating as its greater property, to serve as a tool to link some abstract chemistry concepts with physical components. Teachers appointed that in combination with a didactic strategy, could serve a learning ludic tool. UX's processes application, at each testing stage, allows us to collect valuable information to define customized product's characteristics, and printing features. Furthermore, at the exploration phase, this process supports digital technology selection, and machining processes planning. Different digital fabrication technologies' availability allow us to receive users feedback to, prototype design improvements, and test 3D printing features within the BLV community. In terms of validation results, we can conclude that SLA 3D printing technology presents Braille dots smooth texture, making them easy to read, and without any wrinkles due to printing layers. However, residual printing support provoked users reading disorientation, thus, they will require major post-processes.

Finally, we analyze users' qualitative feedback, timeframe machining process, and budgeting requirements to suggest best final product features. Using ABS material, printed at high resolution allows to manufacture the most suitable product due to its low-cost, and braille dots texture quality. Due to COVID 19 context restriction we could not extend the number of BLV's teachers, and students for testing matters. Thus, the following iteration could be focused on both users segments.

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